
USE OF FACEBOOK SITES BY LIS PROFESSIONALS IN MARATHWADA: A CASE STUDY

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Abstract:

Current research focuses on examining how much, why and how LIS Professionals use Facebook, one of the most popular social networking site, and understanding its impact on education and social interaction. The aim of this study is to examine the purposes of Facebook use in Library and Information Science (LIS) Professionals sample and explore time investment of the professionals to Facebook social network site. The study was focus on to explore social networking site (SNS), Facebook to work as an effective tool for imparting information or knowledge and prove helpful in making awareness among LIS Professionals in Marathwada. Data was collected by means of a questionnaire that was circulated among the LIS Professionals randomly. Present article reports the survey of social networking site, Facebook in making awareness among LIS Professionals. Analysis will help the LIS professionals in deriving the benefits of SNS, Facebook.

Keywords: Facebook, LIS Professionals, College Librarian, Social Networking Sites, Marathwada, Maharashtra and Internet.

Introduction:

SNS such as such as Friendster, CyWorld, and MySpace allow individuals to present themselves, articulate their social networks, and establish or maintain connections with others. These sites can be oriented towards work-related contexts (e.g., LinkedIn.com), romantic relationship initiation (the original goal of Friendster.com), connecting those with shared interests such as music or politics (e.g., MySpace.com), or the college student population (the original incarnation of Facebook.com). Participants may use the sites to interact with people they already know offline or to meet new people. The online social network

application analyzed in this article, Facebook, enables its users to present themselves in an online profile, accumulate “friends” who can post comments on each other’s pages, and view each other’s profiles. Facebook members can also join virtual groups based on common interests, see what classes they have in common, and learn each other’s hobbies, interests, musical tastes, and romantic relationship status through the profiles.

Facebook constitutes a rich site for researchers interested in the affordances of social networks due to its heavy usage patterns and technological capacities that bridge online and offline connections. We

believe that Facebook represents an understudied offline to online trend in that it originally primarily served a geographically-bound community (the campus). When data were collected for this study, membership was restricted to people with a specific host institution email address, further tying offline networks to online membership. In this sense, the original incarnation of Facebook was similar to the wired Toronto neighborhood studied by Hampton and Wellman (e.g., Hampton, 2002; Hampton & Wellman, 2003), who suggest that information technology may enhance place-based community and facilitate the generation of social capital.¹ Previous research suggests that Facebook users engage in “searching” for people with whom they have an offline connection more than they “browse” for complete strangers to meet (Lampe, Ellison, & Steinfield, 2006).

An Overview of Facebook:

Created in 2004, by 2022 Facebook was reported to have more than 2.934 billion registered members (July, 2022) generating 1.6 billion page views each day. The site is tightly integrated into the daily media practices of its users: The typical user spends about 20 minutes a day on the site, and two-thirds of users log in at least once a day (Cassidy, 2006; Needham and Company, 2007). Capitalizing on its success among college students, Facebook launched a high school version in early September 2005. In 2006, the company introduced communities for commercial organizations; as of November 2006, almost 22,000 organizations had Facebook directories (Smith, 2006). In 2006, Facebook was used at over 2,000 United States colleges and was the seventh most popular site on the World Wide Web

with respect to total page views (Cassidy, 2006).

Much of the existing academic research on Facebook has focused on identity presentation and privacy concerns. Looking at the amount of information Facebook participants provide about themselves, the relatively open nature of the information, and the lack of privacy controls enacted by the users, Gross and Acquisti (2005) argue that users may be putting themselves at risk both offline (e.g., stalking) and online (e.g., identify theft). Other recent Facebook research examines student perceptions of instructor presence and self disclosure (Hewitt and Forte, 2006), temporal patterns of use (Golder, Wilkinson, and Huberman, 2007), and the relationship between profile structure and friendship articulation (Lampe, Ellison, and Steinfield, 2007).

In contrast to popular press coverage which has primarily focused on negative outcomes of Facebook use stemming from users’ misconceptions about the nature of their online audience, we are interested in situations in which the intended audience for the profile (such as well-meaning peers and friends) and the actual audience are aligned. We use Facebook as a research context in order to determine whether offline social capital can be generated by online tools. The results of our study show that Facebook use among college-age respondents was significantly associated with measures of social capital.

LIS Professionals in Marathwada:

Generally all the people who are engaged with library and information science subject either as a Librarian or Lecturer or Research Scholar or Technical Assistant or Student are called LIS Professionals. But In LIS Professionals we

have taken here the Assistant Librarian, Deputy Librarian who was working in Marathwada Region.

The name Marathwada identifies one of the five regions in Maharashtra state of India. The region coincides with the Aurangabad Division. There are 8 districts in Marathwada region i.e. Aurangabad, Jalna, Beed, Parbhani, Naned, Latur, Hingoli and Osmanabad. Marathwada is one of six administrative division India's Maharashtra state. Aurangabad division coincides almost perfectly with the Marathwada region of Maharashtra.

Eight questions were asked to them and we have received answers of all of them. We have taken five social networking sites – Facebook, Google+, Twitter, What's Up, YouTube and Yahoo to conduct our study and to reveal LIS Professional's view about them as whether these sites are helpful in making awareness among them or not.

Problem Statement:

There are many studies conducted to find out the impact of social networks on young generation. But the present work is conducted among the LIS Professionals to explore how social networking site Facebook proves helpful in generating awareness.

Review of Literature:

Online social network tools may be of particular utility for individuals who otherwise have difficulties forming and maintaining both strong and weak ties. Some research has shown, for example, that the Internet might help individuals with low psychological well-being due to few ties to friends and neighbors (Bargh and McKenna, 2004). Some forms of computer-mediated communication can

lower barriers to interaction and encourage more self-disclosure (Bargh, McKenna, & Fitzsimons, 2002; Tidwell & Walther, 2002); hence, these tools may enable connections and interactions that would not otherwise occur. For this reason, we explore whether the relationship between Facebook use and social capital is different for individuals with varying degrees of self-esteem (Rosenberg, 1989) and satisfaction with life (Diener, Suh, and Oishi, 1997; Pavot and Diener, 1993), two well-known and validated measures of subjective well-being. This leads to the two following pairs of hypotheses:

Social media, social networking, online communication words used parallelly. Zakaria et al (2010) believes that social media applications have already being accepted by young generations as a platform to socialize, collaborate and learn in an informal and flexible manner although their level of involvement and contribution varies significantly. Al-Daihani's study (2010) explores that the majority of MLIS students are aware of social software applications and they make moderate use of blogs, communication tools and social networking sites. Sheens study among students of the Pakistan reveals that the use of social networking site indicates popularity of facebook.com among these youth more often. The survey of Pew Internet (2010) says that Facebook is the most commonly used social network among adults. Subramanian, et al (2008) reported the findings of study conducted to understand the role of SNS in college student's lives. The figure and statistics shows how Facebook has a very influential role in the lives of young adults. In present paper the investigator has the aim of exploring how LIS Professionals integrated Facebook as a tool helpful in generating awareness.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the role of social networking site, Facebook in creating awareness among LIS Professionals in Marathwada.
- To explore LIS Professionals view about its uses and services.
- To identify potential contribution of Facebook to fill the gaps among LIS Professionals.
- To identify the methods of data collection and analysis.
- To explore how to retrieve the relevant information with the use of Facebook by LIS Professionals.
- To help LIS Professionals to generate a user driven environment and updates user with changing environment.

- To reveal Problems in the use Facebook.

Limitations:

The study is limited to LIS Professionals as we want to reveal uses of Facebook in developing awareness about current happenings, professional information, job opportunities and educational development.

Methodology:

The study was based on survey as were administered among LIS Professionals in Marathwada working as Librarian of randomly. The collected data were analyzed using statistical tools.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The data is analyzed in view to the objectives mentioned in the study as follows:

1. Gender wise Analysis:**Table No 1: Gender Wise Analysis of Respondents**

Sr. No	Gender	Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	125	68%
2	Female	59	32%
	Total	184	100%

The result of this study shows that out of 184 respondents 125 (68%) were male and 59 (32%) were female.

2. Most Used SNS:**Table No 2: Most Used Social Networking Sites**

Sr. No	SNS	Respondents	Percentage
1	What's Up	164	89%
2	Facebook	107	57%
3	You Tube	53	29%
4	Yahoo	49	27%
5	Twitter	28	15%
6	Other	11	6%

It is clear from the above table that What's Up was the most often used Social networking site among LIS Professionals

with 164 (89%)%, Facebook was the second most used SNS with 107 (57%) respondents respectively. You Tube recite

in third position having 53 (29%), Yahoo was in fourth position with 49 (27%), Twitter was in sixth position with 28 (15%) and other for exe, LinkedIn, Ning, Grouply, Blog, Flickr, Photo bucket, Net

log, with 11 (6%) of respondents respectively. Respondents may select more than one checkbox, so percentages may add up to more than 100%.

3. Frequency of Using Facebook:

Table No 3. Frequency of use of Facebook

Sr. No	Frequency	Respondents	Percentage
1	Daily	112	61%
2	Sometime	62	34%
3	Rarely	10	5%
	Total	184	100%

It is observed in the study the out of 184 respondents 112 (61%) of LIS Professionals were use Facebook every

day, 62(34%) used it sometimes, and 10 (5%) rarely used of Facebook respectively.

4. Purpose of Using Facebook:

Table No 4: Purpose of Using Facebook

Sr. No	Purpose	Respondents	Percentage
1	To get interact professionally	122	66%
2	To keep abreast of the latest news & commentaries	110	60%
3	To participating in discussions	87	47%
4	To Express Creativity	82	45%
5	Other	11	6%

It is revealed from the above table that 122 (66%) LIS Professionals were use Facebook to interact professionally, 110 (60%) to use keep abreast of latest news and commentaries, 87(47%) of users to use to participating in discussions of the LIS field, 82 (45%) used to Express Creativity and 11 (6%) used to other for

example to connect LIS Professionals all over the World somebody have says it's very best platform in LIS field, for time pass, To build a strong library network across world with new people and distant friends. Respondents may select more than one checkbox, so percentages may add up to more than 100%.

5. Satisfaction Level of Using Facebook:

Table No 5: Satisfaction Level of use of Facebook in Making Awareness

Sr. No	Satisfaction View	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Agree	126	69%
2	Disagree	15	23%
3	Neutral	43	8%
	Total	184	100%

It is founded that the out of 184 respondents the 126 (69%) LIS Professionals were agree that Facebook

proved helpful in making awareness, 43 (8%) have the neutral opinion and 15 (23%) were disagree with it.

6. Facebook work as a Platform:

Table No 6: Facebook works as a platform to interact beyond barriers of location & Nationality

Sr. No	Satisfaction View	Respondents	Percentage
1	Agree	142	78%
2	Disagree	8	4%
3	Neutral	34	18%
	Total	184	100%

In response to the above question it is founded that 142 (78%) LIS Professionals were of the view that

Facebook actual works as a platform to interact beyond barrier, 35 (18%) were neutral and 8(4%) were disagree with it.

7. Satisfaction of Facebook Users:

Table No 7: Satisfaction of Facebook User

Sr. No	Satisfaction View	Respondents	Percentage
1	Satisfied	108	58%
2	Not Satisfied	16	9%
3	Neutral	60	33%
	Total	184	100%

The result of the study shows that majority of the respondents were satisfied in the use of Facebook with 108(58%), 16

(9%) were neutral and 60 (33%) were not satisfied with it.

8. Problems in Using Facebook:

Table No 8: Problems in Using Facebook

Sr. No	Problems	Respondents	Percentage
1	Lack of time	123	67%
2	Lack of technical support	56	30%
3	No privacy ensured	85	46%
4	It is not useful for education	33	18%
5	It has no role in making awareness	20	11%
6	Other	3	2%

Various problems have been mentioned by the respondents among them 123 (67%) LIS Professionals were of the view that they lacks time to use Facebook, 85 (46%) thought that no privacy secured

in the use of Facebook, 33(18%) have the opinion that it was not useful for educational purpose, 56 (30%) were suffer from technical problem and 20 (11%) were founded that it plays nor role in making

awareness and 3(2%) LIS professionals founded that other problems of using Facebook for example No Permission to use Facebook on duty, it gives information

transfer to both parties. Respondents may select more than one checkbox, so percentages may add up to more than 100%.

Conclusion:

It is observed that most LIS Professionals are connected to each other by Facebook to share experiences, views and participated in creating awareness. It has become one of the largest platforms in the world for sharing real time information. Facebook allows users to interact and collaborate with each other in a social media dialogue as creators of user generated content in a virtual community, in contrast to websites where users are limited to the passive viewing of content that was created for them. The conducted study is an attempt to give an overview of social networking site Facebook and its possible uses for LIS Professionals and to assess how much real transformation this technology can deliver, while deflating reaffirmation and singling out the real value of these innovations.

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